

Cocaine Induced Cardiotoxicity, Hepatotoxicity, Acute Lung Injury, Rhabdomyolysis and Acute Kidney Failure

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ABSTRACT

Cocaine is a central nervous system stimulant with an addictive potential. Despite its ban, it is abused worldwide. Cocaine can be consumed through different routes: nasal, oral, and intravenous. It has the potential to cause damage to different systems in the body including cardiovascular, respiratory, muscular, urinary and hepatobiliary systems. Multisystem damage due to cocaine intoxication is rare in clinical practice. We present the case of a young male patient presented to the emergency room after snorting cocaine and later found unresponsive at home. His diagnostic work up was significant for elevated cardiac enzymes, elevated liver enzymes, acute kidney injury, and rhabdomyolysis. Additionally, the patient was noted to have altered mental status and acute respiratory failure.

Keywords: Cocaine; Acute kidney injury; Hepatotoxicity; Rhabdomyolysis; Cardiotoxicity

Abbreviations: AST-Aspartate transaminase; ALT-Alanine transferase; ALP-Alkaline phosphatase; BUN-Blood urea nitrogen; Cr-Creatinine; CK-Creatine Kinase

INTRODUCTION

Cocaine, also known as benzoyl methyl, has been banned since the 19th century. Despite its ban, it is widely abused worldwide. Cocaine is one of the most used illicit drugs in the United States. It is an addictive substance and a central nervous system stimulant^[1]. In the United States, the use of cocaine has been on the rise since 2011^[2].

Cocaine is known to cause adverse effects in the human body organ systems. These effects include myocardial infarction, vascular thrombosis, stroke, rhabdomyolysis, acute kidney injury, chronic kidney disease and malignant hypertension^[3,4]. We present the case of a young male patient who abuses cocaine and presented to the emergency room with multiorgan system damage secondary to cocaine intoxication.

CASE PRESENTATION

A 28-year-old male with no significant past medical history was brought to the emergency room after he became less responsive at home. According to his partner, she had heard him gurgling respiratory sounds and upon checking in on him, found him unresponsive, covered in vomitus, with blue lips. Emergency medical service (EMS) was called and upon arrival, the patient was noted to be bradypneic with constricted pupils. He was given Narcan and quickly regained consciousness. At the time, he was diaphoretic and tachypneic. Blood sugar from a glucometer at the scene was >528 mg/dl. When the patient became more awake in the emergency room (ER) he complained of generalized body aches. He also reported that he had snorted cocaine before he developed substernal chest discomfort for which he took 2 tablets of Percocet (oxycodone 5mg/acetaminophen 325mg). The pain was described as substernal, squeezing, intermittent, non-radiating, rated as 4/10 and associated with nausea. He denied any similar episodes in the past, as well as shortness of breath, abdominal pain, vomiting, change in urinary or bowel habits.

On examination, Vital signs were: temperature 98.3 °F, pulse 90 beats per minute, blood pressure 141/111 mmHg, oxygen saturation 91% on room air and respiratory rate 30 breaths per minute. Physical examination showed a patient that was alert, oriented in time, place and person, and in respiratory distress as he was using his accessory muscles of respiration. He was tachycardic. Pupils were equal, round and reactive to light.

Initial laboratory investigation revealed, white cell count (WBC) of 26.1k/uL with an absolute neutrophil count of 22.45 K/uL and lymphocyte count of 1.4K/uL, hemoglobin was 17.1g/dl and platelets 277k/Ul; sodium 139 mmol/L, potassium 4.9 mmol/L, blood urea nitrogen 40 mg/dl, creatinine 1.82mg/dl, and glucose 146 mg/dl. Total bilirubin was 0.8mg/dL, aspartate aminotransferase 407 U/L, alanine aminotransferase 307 U/L, alkaline phosphatase 77 U/L, total protein 8g/dL, albumin 5g/dL, creatine kinase (CK) 22078 U/L, and high sensitive troponin 2403ng/L. Urine toxicology was positive for cocaine. Further testing revealed positive hepatitis B surface antibody and negative hepatitis B surface antigen. Anti-neutrophilic antibodies, anti-smooth muscle antibodies, and antimitochondrial antibody were negative while ceruloplasmin was 21 mg/dl and ferritin 93.9ng/ml (all within normal limits)

Computed tomography (CT) of the head was negative for any acute process as shown in the (Figure 1) below.

Figure 1: CT head with annotations showing no acute finding

Chest x ray was done and showed bilateral perihilar consolidation with diffuse patchy opacities within the left lung (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Chest x ray: showing ground glass opacities on the left and perihilar consolidation in brown bilaterally.

A follow up chest CT was done which multifocal pneumonia (Figure 3).

Figure 3: CT chest with annotation showing bilateral opacities.

CT abdomen and pelvis showed normal liver architecture and consistency (Figure 4).

Figure 4: CT abdomen showing liver without lesion or fibrosis

Echocardiogram showed normal left ventricular systolic function and diastolic filling pattern. There were no focal left ventricular wall motion abnormalities, no valvular abnormalities, and a left ventricular ejection fraction was 60%. Electrocardiography showed a heart rate of 97 with nonspecific ST changes (Figure 5).

Figure 5: EKG showing normal sinus rhythm with non-specific ST changes

Due to his increased oxygen requirement and work of breathing, supplemental oxygen was up-titrated from nasal canula to non-rebreather mask then to bilevel positive airway pressure (BIPAP). Lorazepam 2mg was given as needed. Antibiotics were started for possible aspiration pneumonia. Enoxaparin was also initiated for non-ST elevation myocardial ischemia. He was on hydration therapy with lactated ringers at the rate of 150 cc/hour.

His daily laboratory results of troponin, liver enzymes, kidney function and creatine kinase were as shown in (Table 1).

Table 1: Showing patient’s daily liver function enzymes, kidney function, troponin and creatine kinase trends

Hospitalization Days	Reference range	D1	D2	D3	D4	D5
AST	<34 U/L	407	303	203	156	89
ALT	10-49 U/L	307	252	190	76	57
ALP	46-116 U/L	77	74	69	70	73
BUN	7-18 mg/dL	40	37	30	17	16
Cr	0.7-1.3 mg/dL	1.82	1.62	1.31	1.20	1.1
Troponin	0-54 ng/L	2403	4562	3015	2006	806
CK	46-171 U/L	22078	15571	8007	5364	1003

During the 5- day hospitalization period, follow up blood work showed that the WBC, CK, liver enzymes and troponin levels trended down, respiratory function improved and the patient was discharged.

DISCUSSION

Erythroxylum coca is a plant found in countries such as Indonesia, South America, and the West Indies from which cocaine is derived^[5]. Cocaine induced acute toxicity accounts for about 5% to 10% of emergency visits in

the United States^[6]. Cocaine use has been reported to cause damage to certain organ systems in the human body. Regardless of the method of administration which may include nasal insufflation, intravenous route, smoking or oral route it is associated with damage to organ systems such as the cardiovascular system^[7]. Our patient administered cocaine through nasal insufflation.

Several mechanisms have been elucidated regarding how cocaine causes damage to the heart. One of these is mechanisms involves its direct toxic effect on the heart muscles as it blocks the voltage-dependent potassium (K⁺) and sodium (Na⁺⁺) channels found in the sinoatrial node and the myocardium. This effect will cause reduced cardiac contractility leading to prolongation of QT interval and QRS complex. Additionally, cocaine also acts centrally on the sympathetic nervous system causing vasoconstriction, increase in myocardial contractility, and increase in heart rate. This effect can cause an imbalance between oxygen need and demand leading to myocardial ischemia and infarction even in normal coronary arteries and in the absence of cardiovascular risk factors^[8-10].

Another organ affected by cocaine use is the liver. It is reported that cocaine can cause acute and chronic liver toxicity. Hepatic damage can manifest as elevated liver enzymes, acute liver failure, and fulminant liver failure with thrombotic microangiopathy^[11,12].

Cocaine causes damage to the muscular system by causing rhabdomyolysis through its direct toxic effect on the skeletal muscles. Its vasoconstrictive effect leads to muscle ischemia and necrosis^[13]. Additionally, cocaine affects the kidneys through its direct toxic effect which may lead to acute kidney injury and chronic kidney disease^[14,15]. Furthermore, the pulmonary system is another system that is affected by administering cocaine through the nasal route. Cocaine causes several complications in the pulmonary system including alveolar hemorrhage, pulmonary edema, pneumothorax, eosinophilic pneumonia and thromboembolic disease^[16]. The term ‘crack lung’ is known as an acute syndrome that occurs within 48 hours of smoking cocaine (crack) characterized by diffuse alveolar damage and hemorrhagic alveolitis. Clinical manifestations include fever, dyspnea, cough, hemoptysis, and progression to respiratory failure. Chest x-ray findings are usually nonspecific and may include ground glass opacities or diffuse alveolar infiltrates^[17].

Our case represents an atypical or rare presentation of cocaine induced multi organ damage. The patient presented with injury to the above-mentioned organ systems affected by cocaine use. He had acute respiratory failure and was placed on BIPAP for oxygen supplementation and antibiotics were initiated due to his chest x-ray findings suggestive of pneumonia. Myocardial ischemia was managed medically with Enoxaparin. He received fluid hydration with lactated ringers at a rate of 150 cc/hour and his kidney function, liver enzymes and creatine kinase (CK) level were monitored daily.

CONCLUSION

Cocaine is a central nervous system stimulant with a high potency of addiction. It causes damage to bodily systems irrespective of its route of administration. Our case illustrates a rare scenario in which the patient presented with multiorgan involvement due to cocaine use, thus requiring a multidisciplinary team approach in the management. This paper highlights the adverse effects of cocaine use and the importance of counseling cocaine abusers about these complications in an outpatient setting.

DISCLOSURES

All authors have no disclosures.

REFERENCES

1. Zimmerman JL. Cocaine intoxication. Crit Care Clin. 2012;28(4):517-526.
2. Cano M, Oh S, Salas CP, Vaughn MG. Cocaine use and overdose mortality in the United States: Evidence from two national data sources, 2002-2018. Drug Alcohol Depend. 2020;1(214):108148.
3. Riezzo I, Fiore C, Pascale N. Side effects of cocaine abuse: multiorgan toxicity and pathological consequences. Curr Med Chem. 2012;19(33):5624-5646.
4. Nzerue CM, Lowe HK, Riley LJ Jr. Cocaine and the kidney: a synthesis of pathophysiologic and clinical perspectives. Am J Kidney Dis. 2000;35(5):783-795.
5. Goldstein RA, DesLauriers C, Burda A, Arbor JK. Cocaine: history, social implications, and toxicity: a review. Semin Diagn Pathol. 2009;26(1):10-17.
6. Maraj S, Figueredo VM, Morris LD. Cocaine and the heart. Clin Cardiol. 2010;33(5):264-269.
7. Dave D. The effects of cocaine and heroin price on drug-related emergency department visits. J Health Econ. 2006;25(2):311-333.
8. Sarkar A, Pande A, Naveen Chandra GS, Ahmed I. Acute myocardial infarction in a young cocaine addict with normal coronaries: time to raise awareness among emergency physicians. Indian J Crit Care Med. 2013;17(1):56-58.
9. Wood DM, Dargan PI, Hoffman RS. Management of cocaine-induced cardiac arrhythmias due to cardiac ion channel dysfunction. Clin Toxicol (Phila). 2009;47(1):14-23.
10. Vongpatanasin W, Mansour Y, Chavoshan B, Arbique D, Victor RG. Cocaine stimulates the human cardiovascular system via a central mechanism of action. Circulation. 1999;100(5):497-502.
11. Balaguer F, Fernández J, Lozano M, Miquel R, Mas A. Cocaine-induced acute hepatitis and thrombotic microangiopathy. JAMA. 2005;293(7):797-798.
12. 12. Payancé A, Scotto B, Perarnau JM, Muret A, Bacq Y. Severe chronic hepatitis secondary to prolonged use of ecstasy and cocaine. Clin Res Hepatol Gastroenterol. 2013;37(5):e109-113.
13. Alardín HAL, Varon J, Marik PE. Bench-to-bedside review: Rhabdomyolysis -- an overview for clinicians. Crit Care. 2005;9(2):158-169.
14. Singh VP, Singh N, Jaggi AS. A review on renal toxicity profile of common abusive drugs. Korean J Physiol Pharmacol. 2013;17(4):347-357.
15. Buettner M, Toennes SW, Buettner S, et al. Nephropathy in illicit drug abusers: a postmortem analysis. Am J Kidney Dis. 2014;63(6):945-53.
16. Restrepo CS, Carrillo JA, Martínez S, Ojeda P, Rivera AL, Hatta A. Pulmonary complications from cocaine and cocaine-based substances: imaging manifestations. Radiographics. 2007;27(4):941-956.
17. Forrester JM, Steele AW, Waldron JA, Parsons PE. Crack lung: an acute pulmonary syndrome with a spectrum of clinical and histopathologic findings. Am Rev Respir Dis. 1990;142(2):462-7.